

1
2
3
4
5
6
7
8
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28

PAX8 mediates resistance to trastuzumab in HER2+ breast cancer.

Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹
¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com
Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467
East Islip, NY USA 11730

Homeobox expression (like that of PAX8) is central to transformation, and maintains a transformed state. We demonstrated a function for homeoboxes as mediator of resistance responses in humans with cancer by studying the tumor transcriptomes of humans with HER2+ breast cancer achieving pathologic complete response (pCR) in comparison to that of patients who failed to achieve complete response (PR, or partial response), which we interpret as disease resistance, identifying PAX1. Here, we identified PAX8 as a top effector of trastuzumab resistance. The data suggest essential differences in primary transformation versus acquisition of resistance with respect to actors that support an oncogenic cellular system.